

ICCM22
MELBOURNE
AUSTRALIA

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

Understanding Residual Stress in Rapid-Curing Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymer Composites

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Overview

Fast curing
thermoset resin system

High temperature

Increasing production rate

Decreasing mechanical properties
(Fatigue life)

Stress-Free Temperature

Temperature activated relaxation

$$\sigma_A = \frac{1}{d_A} \left(\frac{(\alpha_B - \alpha_A)\Delta T}{\frac{1 - \nu_A}{d_A E_A} + \frac{1 - \nu_B}{d_B E_B}} \right)$$

$$\Delta T = T_{SF} - T$$

Direct relationship
between T_{SF} and Residual Stress

Shape Distortion

- Thermal Contraction (CTE)
- Chemical Shrinkage
- Tool-Part Interactions

Curing Profile (RTM)

Results

Precise detection of T_{SF} for partially and fully cured composite

The influence of post-curing temperature on T_{SF}

Modified post-curing to reduce T_{SF}

Summary

Residual stress is one of the major hurdles for manufacturing fast-curing composite parts. To understand and reduce the residual stress it is critical to identify the **stress free temperature**. In this study:

- ✓ Stress-free temperature was successfully identified through relaxation and deflection tests.
- ✓ It was proven that the measured T_{SF} was lower than the curing temperature.
- ✓ Initial experiments confirmed that the final deflection and T_{SF} can be successfully reduced by equilibrating at T_{SF} before the ultimate post-curing process.